

**NECESSITY OF INTEGRATING SPECIALISTS THROUGH A
COMBINATION OF EDUCATION AND PRACTICAL EXPERIENCE IN
THE WORKPLACE IN THE ERA OF THE DIGITAL ECONOMY IN
UZBEKISTAN.**

¹Akhunova Sh.N, ²Askarov F.R, ³Numanov J.O.

¹PhD in Economics, FerPI, ²Master in Economics, FerPI, ACCA student, ³Master in Economics,
FerPI student

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10159788>

Abstract. *This thesis examines the necessity of integrating specialists through a combination of education and practical experience in the workplace, focusing on the context of Uzbekistan's digital economy era. The rapid advancement of technology and the digital transformation of industries present unique challenges and opportunities for specialists in Uzbekistan. To thrive in this dynamic environment, it is crucial for specialists to possess not only theoretical knowledge but also practical skills relevant to the digital economy.*

Through a comprehensive literature review, this study explores the benefits and importance of integrating education and practical experience in developing a well-rounded workforce. Drawing on case studies and empirical evidence, the research highlights the positive impact of such integration on enhancing specialists' adaptability, problem-solving abilities, and overall professional growth.

The thesis also examines the specific context of Uzbekistan's digital economy, considering the country's unique socio-economic factors and policy initiatives. By analyzing existing educational frameworks, workplace practices, and government strategies, this research aims to provide practical recommendations for effectively integrating specialists in Uzbekistan's digital economy era.

The findings of this study contribute to the existing literature on talent development and workforce readiness in the digital era. The insights gained from this research can inform policymakers, educational institutions, and employers in Uzbekistan, helping them design and implement strategies that foster a skilled and agile workforce capable of driving innovation and economic growth in the digital economy.

Keywords: *Digital economy, integration, practical experience, Internet of Things, IT specialists, e-business, e-commerce*

Introduction: In the era of digitalization across all sectors and activities, particularly in the context of the digital economy, it is crucial to recognize that theoretical knowledge alone, without practical experience, can result in a loss of knowledge before its application in real-life situations. This becomes increasingly significant in a world where technology is advancing at an exponential rate.

The rapid pace of technological development requires professionals to not only understand theoretical concepts but also to be adept at applying them in practical scenarios. Without hands-on experience, theories can quickly become outdated or insufficient to address the complexities of the digital landscape.

Practical experience allows individuals to develop critical skills such as problem-solving, adaptability, and innovation, which are essential in navigating the ever-evolving world of

technology. It enables professionals to stay abreast of the latest trends and advancements, ensuring their knowledge remains relevant and effective.

Moreover, the exponential growth curve of technology signifies that new breakthroughs and innovations emerge at an accelerating pace. By integrating practical experience with theoretical education, professionals can continuously update their skills and knowledge, keeping up with the rapid changes in the digital economy.

A specialist in the field of the digital economy is an individual who possesses knowledge in both economic sciences and practical computer sciences, including both hardware and software aspects. The labor market has a high demand for such specialists. However, it is crucial to emphasize the importance of practical experience.

In the modern world, the rapid development and updates of programs and improved hardware mean that knowledge can quickly become outdated. Until a student acquires a comprehensive understanding of a particular field, new advancements may have already surpassed their current knowledge. Therefore, it is essential for individuals to combine theoretical knowledge with practical experience.

Grasping knowledge alone is insufficient. The integration of practical experience allows individuals to stay up to date with the latest advancements and trends in the digital economy. By actively engaging in real-life scenarios, professionals can develop problem-solving skills, adapt to new technologies, and effectively apply their knowledge.

The combination of theory and practice ensures that specialists in the digital economy field possess relevant and up-to-date expertise. It enables them to navigate the dynamic nature of the digital landscape and contribute meaningfully to their organizations and the broader digital economy.

In developed countries, education frameworks often include compulsory education up to a certain age, followed by various pathways for further education and training. These pathways can include vocational education and training (VET) programs, apprenticeships, higher education institutions, and professional development opportunities.

For instance, the EU has various initiatives and frameworks in place to promote and support specialist training and professional development across its member states.

One such initiative is the European Qualifications Framework (EQF), which provides a common reference framework for qualifications across Europe. The EQF facilitates transparency and comparability of qualifications, including those obtained through specialist training programs.

Additionally, the EU supports vocational education and training (VET) through programs such as Erasmus+ and the European Social Fund (ESF). These programs aim to enhance the quality of VET, promote mobility and cooperation among VET institutions, and support the acquisition of specialized skills.

Furthermore, there are sector-specific professional organizations and associations in the EU that focus on specialist training and development within specific fields. These organizations often collaborate with educational institutions, employers, and policymakers to ensure high standards of specialist training and to address the needs of the labor market.

In the United States, education and training frameworks are primarily structured at the state and local levels, although there are also federal initiatives that provide guidance and support. Here are some key elements of the education and training framework in the USA:

1. **K-12 Education:** Education in the United States typically begins with kindergarten (K) at around age 5, followed by 12 years of primary and secondary education. Each state has its own standards and curriculum guidelines, although the Common Core State Standards have been adopted by many states to ensure consistency in English language arts and mathematics education.
2. **Higher Education:** The United States has a robust higher education system consisting of universities, colleges, and community colleges. Higher education typically includes undergraduate (bachelor's) degrees, graduate (master's and doctoral) degrees, and professional degrees. Accreditation is an important aspect, ensuring that institutions meet certain quality standards.
3. **Vocational Education and Career and Technical Education (CTE):** Vocational education and CTE programs provide specialized training and education to prepare students for specific trades, occupations, or industries. These programs often include hands-on learning experiences, internships, and industry partnerships to help students develop practical skills.
4. **Workforce Development Programs:** Workforce development programs aim to enhance the skills and employability of individuals in the workforce. These programs can include job training, apprenticeships, on-the-job training, and initiatives like the Workforce Innovation and Opportunity Act (WIOA) that provide funding and support for workforce development activities.
5. **Lifelong Learning:** Lifelong learning is encouraged through various initiatives such as adult education programs, continuing education courses, and online learning platforms. These opportunities enable individuals to acquire new skills, stay updated with industry trends, and adapt to changing job market needs throughout their careers.
6. **Federal Initiatives:** The U.S. Department of Education plays a role in providing federal guidance and funding for education programs. Additionally, federal agencies such as the Department of Labor and the Department of Commerce support workforce development initiatives and collaborate with state and local entities to align education and training with industry demands.

It's important to note that education and training frameworks can vary across states and regions in the United States due to the decentralized nature of the education system. Each state has its own policies, standards, and funding mechanisms, resulting in some variations in curriculum, graduation requirements, and vocational training offerings.

Integration of education and practice is a common focus in several countries, including Japan, South Korea, Australia, Canada, and Singapore. Although each country has its own unique approach;

In Japan, there is emphasis on practical training and experiential learning in addition to academic education. The country's education system aims to foster a balance between theoretical knowledge and hands-on practical skills. Vocational education and training (VET) programs are available to provide specialized training in various industries. Work-integrated learning and apprenticeship programs are also common in Japan, allowing students to gain practical experience while studying.

South Korea places a strong emphasis on practical education and vocational training. The country has a well-developed vocational education system that combines classroom learning with work experience. Students can choose vocational high schools or specialized vocational colleges

to acquire practical skills relevant to specific industries. Work-based learning programs and internships are frequently integrated into the curriculum to provide real-world experience.

Australia has a strong focus on integrating education and practice through its vocational education and training (VET) sector. The country offers a wide range of VET programs, which emphasize hands-on learning and practical skills relevant to industry needs. Apprenticeships and traineeships are common pathways for individuals to gain practical experience while working towards qualifications. Industry collaboration and partnerships are encouraged to ensure that training programs align with industry demands.

In Canada, the integration of education and practice is highly valued. The country has a well-established system of vocational education and training, delivered through colleges and institutes. Cooperative education programs and apprenticeships are popular in Canada, allowing students to alternate between classroom learning and work placements. These programs provide practical experience and help students develop skills that are directly applicable to their chosen fields.

Singapore places significant emphasis on the integration of education and practice to prepare its workforce for the demands of the economy. The country has a strong vocational education and training system, offering a range of skills-based programs and apprenticeships. Institutes of Higher Learning (IHLs) collaborate closely with industry partners to develop curriculum and provide work-based learning opportunities. The SkillsFuture initiative in Singapore encourages lifelong learning and supports individuals in acquiring practical skills throughout their careers.

Overall, these countries recognize the importance of integrating education and practice to develop a skilled and adaptable workforce. They offer various pathways, such as vocational education, work-integrated learning, apprenticeships, and industry partnerships, to ensure that individuals acquire both theoretical knowledge and practical skills necessary for their chosen fields.

It is important to highlight two significant challenges that developing countries often face when it comes to integrating education and practice: limited availability of internships in the students' field of study and a potential mismatch between the level of education and the local economic conditions. These challenges can hinder the practical training and application of knowledge for students and future specialists.

In some developing countries like Uzbekistan, there may be a shortage of opportunities for students to engage in internships or work placements specifically related to their field of study. This can occur due to several reasons, such as a lack of well-established industry partnerships, limited resources, or a mismatch between the skills demanded by the job market and the skills developed through education programs.

To address this challenge, developing countries can explore various strategies. These may include fostering collaboration between educational institutions and industries to create internship programs, establishing partnerships with local businesses, and promoting entrepreneurship and innovation. Government initiatives, such as providing incentives for companies to offer internships or creating internship subsidy programs, can also help expand opportunities for students to gain practical experience.

Another challenge can arise when the education system in a developing country offers programs that are highly advanced or not aligned with the local economic conditions and job

market demands. This can lead to a disconnect between the skills and knowledge acquired through education and the practical requirements of local industries.

To address this challenge, it is essential for educational institutions and policymakers to actively engage with industries and employers to identify the skills and competencies that are in demand. This can be done through regular industry consultations, labor market assessments, and collaboration with professional bodies and associations. By aligning educational programs with local economic needs, developing countries can ensure that students are equipped with practical skills that are relevant and valuable in the job market.

Research and Methodology:

1) *the analysis and synthesis method* is employed to uncover the conceptual and categorical framework of research and provide a scientific rationale for the pedagogical conditions required in the professional training of specialists in the field of digital economics.

2) *scientific abstraction, induction and deduction* are employed when summarizing the Uzbekistan’s experience of specialists’ professional training in the economic sector at higher education institutions in the Republic of Uzbekistan.

3) *The abstract-logical approach* is utilized to theoretically generalize the research findings and formulate conclusions.

4) *Mathematical and statistical processing of research results* involves analyzing the collected data through various techniques such as ranking, scaling, registration, systematization, differentiation, grouping, and graphical representation.

The reality of nations and regions is that they are constantly changing in response to predictable as well as unpredictable changes in their environments. Governments respond to change through policy making which is assumed to be a rational decision making process but is often political. Apthorpe [3] suggests that policy practice is actually about who is included and what ignored or excluded. The style of policy discourses is to talk as though that were not so, but as though the data were inclusive, the process rational and the remedy simply knowledge or research based [3]. Development policy he suggests is embedded in discourse and composed of “urgent and unavoidable utterances” that distinguishes itself from its practices and operations by treating them as something else called implementation. At the same time policy discourse has recourse to neat, easily available and powerfully constructed sets of institutional, legislative and financial resources [3][4].

In addition, the use of microcomputers and packaged software for complex modeling and forecasting of macro-economic trends has reduced the cost of providing macroeconomic analysis services and opened up opportunities for sharing of data and collaboration among Latin American countries and the USA [5]. However, these models are only as good as the data that is fed into them and in Latin American countries six months is the longest term that can be predicted with any accuracy [5]. This makes it difficult to forecast macroeconomic trends into the long term or compare the data among countries with accuracy. This may lead to predictions that cannot always be verified nor may be sufficiently accurate. Joseph A Schumpeter [1] adds that economic theory of development is based on a set of static assumptions that if held true will bring about a certain set of results. However the reality of development lies in that it is an ever changing, complex phenomenon that alludes researchers trying define it into variables. Fullerton [5] explained that just one model he developed for a sector for a Latin American Country had over 100 variables. He concludes that good forecasts always relay upon local observations as much as they do on strong

theoretical and empirical frameworks. Even in an era of unprecedented computational advances, successful economists must have an ear to the ground [5].

As we witness the rapid exponential growth of technologies, it becomes imperative to ensure that students' knowledge and practical skills are aligned with this evolving landscape. Labor, being an integral component of goods and services in the economy, typically exhibits price elasticity of demand. Similarly, from the supply side perspective, educational institutions, as providers of labor through the training of students, should strive to enhance the elasticity of labor supply in response to market demands.

In accordance with Presidential Decree # 3775 “Regarding measures to enhance the quality of education in higher education institutions and promote their active participation in wide-ranging reforms being implemented in the country”, issued on 26th of September, 2018, has been developed the system of monitoring and evaluating students' knowledge in higher education institutions[6]. With initiative of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M.Mirziyayev and the Presidential Decree # 5847 “Regarding the approval of the Concept for the Development of the Higher Education System of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030”, issued on 8th of October, 2019, set the objectives and aims such as:

- To ensure that at least 10 higher education institutions in the Republic are recognized by international organizations such as Quacquarelli Symonds World University Rankings, Times Higher Education, or Academic Ranking of World Universities.

- To strive for the inclusion of these recognized institutions in the top 1,000 ranking of higher education institutions worldwide.

Specifically, the National University of Uzbekistan and Samarkand State University should aim to be listed among the top 500 higher education institutions in the future.

These objectives and aims are geared towards enhancing the reputation and international recognition of selected higher education institutions in the Republic of Uzbekistan. By striving for recognition and improved rankings, it is anticipated that these institutions will attract global attention and contribute to the advancement of the higher education sector in Uzbekistan [7].

According to the Ministry of Higher Education, Science, and Innovations of the Republic of Uzbekistan's data, there are 212 higher education institutions in Uzbekistan, with 30 being foreign (joint/branch) institutions, 66 private institutions, and 116 public institutions. In 2023, the total number of students in Uzbekistan reached 1,203,125. These figures reflect the current state of higher education institutions in Uzbekistan as per the official statistics [8].

Table 1. Statistical information on education and social spheres.

Sphere \ year	2021	2022	2023
Number of students enrolled in Business and management	19 906	30 756	26 569
Number of students enrolled in Information and communication technologies.	10 407	16 066	19 306

Source: compiled by the authors [8]

A new paradigm of accelerated economic development based on real-time data exchange... is a system of economic, social and cultural relations based on the use of digital information and communication technologies [9] “...The digital economy, the implementation of business transactions in markets based on the Internet and the World Wide Web” [10] Ceteris paribus, in the context of the digital economy, the labor force is assumed to be a combination of skills in

economics, business, and technology. In the digital economy, students play a vital role as drivers of growth and development. Their expertise in economics, business, and technology fuels innovation and propels digital transformation across sectors. Simultaneously, the internet and networks serve as the lifeblood, providing essential infrastructure and connectivity for information, data, and transactions. Acting as the backbone of digital technologies, platforms, and services, they enable communication, collaboration, and the exchange of goods and services. Through the active participation of students and a robust internet and network infrastructure, the digital economy flourishes, fostering innovation, productivity, and economic growth.

Table 2. Number of active organizations by types of economic activity "Information and Communication" (as of January 1, 2023, units).

Industries	2021	2022	2023
Release of computer games	136	130	156
Release of other software	315	352	425
Computer programming activities	896	1121	1618
Consulting services in the field of computer technology	387	461	536
Computer equipment management activities	198	243	290
Other activities in the field of information technology and computer systems	1 433	1 596	1 993
Data placement and processing services	510	628	704

Source: compiled by the authors [11]

The increasing number of software developers is contributing to the growth of related products and services in various industries. This trend can be observed by comparing the increase in activities such as the release of computer games and other software programming activities, as indicated in Table 2. The availability of the internet plays a significant role in this expansion, as it enables greater access to software products and services. Additionally, the increasing supply of software-related products leads to a more price elastic market, meaning that changes in price have a greater impact on demand. As a result, the software industry continues to experience growth and innovation, driven by the increasing number of skilled developers and the accessibility of digital platforms.

The efficient utilization of the internet depends on the quality of its users. As indicated in Table 1, the number of qualified users is increasing, leading to a potential exponential increase in the efficiency of the rate of return on money spent on the internet. The quality of users, including their skills, knowledge, and proficiency, plays a crucial role in maximizing the benefits derived from internet usage. Furthermore, modern programming compilers often operate online, underscoring the importance of factors such as internet speed, connection quality, and pricing. These key factors directly influence the overall experience and productivity of users, emphasizing the need for reliable and affordable internet services to ensure optimal utilization of online resources.

Table 3. The volume of rendered market communication and informatization services (in actual prices, billion soums)

Indicators	2020	2021	2022
programming and broadcasting services	650,9	696,7	833,1

telecommunication services	10 233,7	11 957,3	14 660,7
computer programming services, consulting and other related services	1 428,2	2 721,5	4 652,9
information services	708,7	1 373,6	2 516,0

Source: compiled by the authors [11]

The projection of an increasing qualified labor force and the rise in educated internet users is creating a growing market for computer services. This trend is evident when examining Table 3, which shows that the number of computer programming services has nearly doubled each year over the past three consecutive years. The demand for computer services is fueled by the expanding pool of skilled professionals and the increasing reliance on technology in various industries. As businesses and individuals seek specialized software development, IT consulting, and other computer-related services, the market for computer services experiences significant growth. This presents opportunities for businesses operating in this sector to meet the rising demand and capitalize on the expanding market.

Table 4. E-commerce includes the sale of products (goods, works, services) under contracts concluded using information systems, including through an offer, exchanges and auctions, as well as using other electronic trading platforms. (for 2022 preliminary data).

Indicators	2020	2021	2022
Sector of information economy and e-commerce	10 777,0	16 939,5	27 791,2
Sector of information and communication technologies (ICT)	9 095,9	11 567,6	16 089,9
ICT production	540,1	503,3	805,5
ICT trade	252,3	367,8	594,0
ICT services	8 303,5	10 696,4	14 690,4
Content sector and mass media	1 089,7	1 464,6	1 944,9
E-commerce	591,4	3 907,3	9 756,4

Source: compiled by the authors [11]

The e-commerce sector, as a vital component of the digital economy, has experienced exponential growth, with its volume nearly tripling, in accordance with Table 4. This sector holds significant importance as it requires minimal face-to-face training compared to industries such as banking, credit services, and insurance, which often necessitate physical presence at the workplace for trainees or students. In contrast, e-commerce and e-business operations can be conducted remotely, making it a particularly attractive sector for individuals in developing countries like Uzbekistan. The burgeoning e-commerce market offers ample opportunities for students and future specialists to thrive and carve out their niche in a rapidly expanding industry. By leveraging their skills and knowledge in the digital realm, individuals can tap into this fresh market and contribute to the continued growth and success of the e-commerce sector.

Table 5. The share of households in the Republic of Uzbekistan with access to the Internet, by type of services (according to the sample survey of households, as a percentage).

Series Name	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
Fixed (wired) narrowband network	1,1	0,6	0,6	1,0	1,2
Fixed (wired) broadband network	2,4	0,3	1,2	1,8	3,6

Terrestrial fixed (wireless) broadband network	5,3	6,6	8,1	11,7	13,9
Satellite broadband network (via satellite communication)	0	4,9	5,1	3,6	3,3
Mobile broadband network using a portable device	68,2	84,2	86,1	78,3	85,7
Mobile broadband network using an integrated SIM card in a computer or USB modem	9,7	1,6	0,2	6,6	6,7

Source: compiled by the authors [11]

The World Bank has suggested the need to enhance Information and Communication Technology skills in all sectors because a 10% increase in internet connectivity was found to boost GDP growth by 1.38%. Simultaneously, the OECD argued that high internet access rates generate a 2% increase in GDP. Because the internet positively affects economic growth, we investigated the relationship between an economically active population, human capital and technology to evaluate these effects in Mexico. A data series from 1991 to 2010 was analysed in three stages according to the least-squares method. A Cobb–Douglas function under the Solow model was considered. Technology and internet access were found to positively affect top-level students and graduate students and thus contribute to the global innovation index[12].

Table 5 demonstrates that the percentage of mobile internet users has remained relatively consistent over the past 3-4 years, while the number of fixed broadband users has doubled. This is largely due to the increased accessibility of internet services through landline cables in Uzbekistan. This trend is highly beneficial for IT developers, as modern programming compilers like Android Studio and Visual Studio often rely on online compiling. Continuous updates and uninterrupted internet access are crucial for software development, as any disruptions can potentially cause damage to both software and, in some cases, hardware. This is a concern not only for countries with average global income but also for developed nations, as unexpected expenses can be detrimental to citizens' financial well-being. Therefore, the positive trend of expanding access to fixed broadband in Uzbekistan is advantageous for IT developers and contributes to the overall stability and efficiency of software development processes.

Conclusion:

While theoretical knowledge is vital, it must be complemented by practical experience. The integration of theory and practice equips specialists with the necessary skills and adaptability to thrive in the ever-evolving digital economy.

In conclusion, it is crucial for the government of Uzbekistan to develop a comprehensive framework that promotes practical engagement for students and learners across all fields, not just in economics. In the digital era, it is essential for the government to prioritize the health and safety of internet users while also focusing on increasing the overall number of internet users. This can be achieved through initiatives that provide educational programs, resources, and support for individuals to navigate the digital landscape safely. Additionally, efforts to expand internet infrastructure and accessibility will play a vital role in enabling more citizens to benefit from the opportunities offered by the digital world. By addressing these aspects, the government can foster a conducive environment for learning, innovation, and overall development in Uzbekistan.

To help achieve the goals outlined in the Uzbekistan 2030 strategy, here are three suggestions:

Increase Internet Network Coverage: Expanding internet network coverage across the country is crucial to ensure that all citizens have access to the digital world. This can be achieved by investing in infrastructure development, including the installation of broadband cables, mobile towers, and satellite connectivity. By improving internet network coverage, more individuals, including students and professionals, will have the opportunity to benefit from online education, remote work, and digital services.

Foster Competition Between Students and Professionals: Promoting healthy competition among students and professionals in all fields can drive innovation and excellence. This can be accomplished through the establishment of competitions, hackathons, and events that encourage participants to showcase their skills and knowledge. Providing platforms for collaboration and recognition will not only motivate individuals to excel but also contribute to the overall growth and competitiveness of various industries.

Allocate Subsidies for Hardware Purchases: Recognizing the importance of access to hardware for success in the digital era, the government can consider allocating subsidies or financial assistance to deserving students and individuals. This would help reduce the financial burden of purchasing hardware such as laptops, tablets, and smartphones, enabling students to engage in online learning and professionals to work more efficiently. By supporting the acquisition of necessary hardware, the government can empower students and professionals to fully participate in the digital economy.

These suggestions aim to enhance connectivity, foster a competitive environment, and support individuals in acquiring essential tools for success in the digital age. By implementing these measures, Uzbekistan can make significant progress towards its 2030 strategy and create a more inclusive and thriving digital ecosystem.

REFERENCES

1. Schumpeter, J. A. (2002) “The economy as a whole: Seventh chapter of The Theory of Economic Development” *Industry and Innovation*, 9, 1/2, 93-145.
2. Apthorpe, R. (1994) “Development Theory Now.” *European Journal of Development Research*, 6, 2, 182-188.
3. Apthorpe, R., (1999) “Development studies and policy studies: in the short run we are all dead.” *Journal of International Development*, 11, 4, 535 – 547.
4. Qureshi, S. (2005). How does information technology effect development? Integrating theory and practice into a process model.
5. Fullerton, T. M., Jr. (1992) “The PC Corner: Confessions of an International Forecaster.” *Business Economics*, 27, 2, 61- 65.
6. Presidential Decree # 3775 “Regarding measures to enhance the quality of education in higher education institutions and promote their active participation in wide-ranging reforms being implemented in the country”, issued on 26th of September, 2018
7. Presidential Decree # 5847 “Regarding the approval of the Concept for the Development of the Higher Education System of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030”, issued on 8th of October, 2019
8. <https://stat.edu.uz/>

9. Развитие цифровой экономики в России // Всемирный банк 20 дек. 2016. URL: <http://www.vseмирnyjbank.org/ru/events/2016/12/20/developing-the-digital-economy-in-russia-internationalseminar-1>
10. The Digital Economy. London: British Computer Society, 2014. URL: http://policy.bcs.org/ites/policy.bcs.org/files/digital%20economy%20Final%20version_0.pdf
11. <https://stat.uz/uz/rasmiy-statistika/raqamli-iqtisodiyot>
12. Jiménez, M., Matus, J. A., & Martínez, M. A. (2014). Economic growth as a function of human capital, internet and work. *Applied economics*, 46(26), 3202-3210.